

International Journal of Marketing & Financial Management (IJMFM)

ISSN: 2348 -3954 (Online)

ISSN: 2349 -2546 (Print)

Email us: editor@arseam.com

<http://www.arseam.com/>

Download Full Paper:

<http://www.arseam.com/content/volume-2-issue-10-nov-2014>

**Impact
Factor:
0.98**

THE STUDY OF CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR TOWARDS DIFFERENT MOBILE BRANDS

Dr Sukhvir Singh

Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce
University of Delhi, Delhi

Abstract

The mobile phone has made our life easily. We can perform different task of our daily life on mobile phones in few seconds. We can transfer money, pay utility bills by using mobile phones in few seconds for which we have to go to banks that takes a lot of time. The aim of the study is to cover entire research to know the various factors that influence decision-making in purchasing a mobile phone and to study various factors that can increase the sale of mobile phones. sample of 200 customers of mobile phone users is taken. Questionnaire has been analysed with the help of pie diagram & bar chart and different interpretations have been made to study the impact. The study concluded that SAMSUNG has the maximum brand preference as compared to other brands. APPLE is well trusted and appreciated brand. Most of the dealers are selling more than one brand. They sell different brands to gain more volume & more availability to the customers.

Keywords: Samsung, Apple, Mobile

Introduction: In the early 1990s, the Indian government adopted a new economic policy aimed at improving India's competitiveness in the global markets and the rapid growth of exports. Key to achieving these goals was a world-class telecom infrastructure.

- In India, the telecom service areas are divided into four metros (New Delhi, Mumbai, Chennai and Kolkata) and 20 circles, which roughly correspond to the states in India. The circles are further classified under "A," "B" and "C," with the "A" circle being the most attractive and "C" being the least attractive. The regulatory body at that time — the Department of Telecommunications (DOT) — allocated two cellular licenses for each metro and circle. Thirty-four licenses for GSM900 cellular services were auctioned to 22 firms in 1995.

- In 1996, the Telecom Regulatory Authority of India (TRAI) bill was introduced in the Lok Sabha, and the president officially announced the TRAI ordinance on 25 January 2003. The government decided to set up TRAI to separate regulatory functions from policy formulation, licensing and telecom operations. Prior to the creation of TRAI, these functions were the sole responsibility of the DOT. APPLE, Inc. has been at the forefront of communication inventions and innovations for nearly 40 years since its invention by STEVE JOBS on April 1, 1976. We have achieved extraordinary accomplishments along the way .

Today, APPLE develops a portfolio of consumer electronics, personal computers, servers, and computer software, and is a digital distributor of media content that takes mobile experiences to a new level. With the rapid convergence of fixed and mobile broadband Internet and the growing demand for next-generation mobile communication solutions, our mission is to lead the next wave of innovative products that meet the expanding needs of our customers around the world.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Mobile phones are a part of status symbol (**Walsh & White 2006**) and represent a lifestyle which a user wants to project in front of his society (Katz 2003). Status conscious consumers of Indian market have included certain brands of mobile handset to express their preferred identity in front of others. Branded mobile phones are considered as emblematic gadgets of personal identities. The users who are willing to spend more on this gadget for gaining the ownership of a particular brand name are falling under the phenomenon.

It is described by **Katz (2003)** as “machines that become us”. Different research studies show the nature of mobile handset buyers. Some of them have pointed out the differences between purchasing habits of young and old generations while some others have projected mobile phone as a gender neutral device (Bianchi & Phillips 2005), which is meant for all consumer categories.

Trendy designs with ground-breaking features are considered as a primal rule of purchase among young consumers (Mack & Sharples, 2009) than older ones (**Barak and Gould, 1985**)

In **Keller’s (1993, 2009)** model of CBBE, he has proposed brand equity existed in consumer minds can be called as consumer based brand equity.

Objective of the Study

- To know the various factors that influence decision-making in Purchasing a mobile phone.
- To find out the brand awareness of APPLE in the market.
- To study various factors that can increase the sale of mobile phones.

Research Methodology

Research design used- Exploratory Research design

SAMPLING METHODOLOGY:

Sampling Location – Delhi

Sampling Technique - Random Sampling technique

Sampling Size – 200 respondents

DATA COLLECTION:

- Primary data has been used in the form of Questionnaire & Observation, which are the two basic methods of collecting primary data, which suffices all research objectives.
- Secondary data sources like catalogue of the company, product range book of the company & various internet sites such as APPLE.com & google.com have been used.

ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATION

1.) Which company handset are you using?

Different mobile phone brands	Number of respondents using it
SAMSUNG	80
APPLE	60
MICROMAX	30
NOKIA	10
OTHER BRANDS	20

Interpretation:-

The above chart shows the percentage of various handsets used by the respondents. Out of 20 respondents, 8 are using Samsung phones, 6 people are using Apple, 3 are using Micromax, 1 Nokia and 2 are using others. Above analysis shows that Nokia has the maximum customers. Apple is just behind Samsung because Apple product is relatively expensive being in comparison with Samsung.

2. Are you satisfied with your handset or not?

Response	Number of respondents
YES	16
NO	4

Interpretation:-

The pie chart shows that maximum people are satisfied with their handsets. Out of 20 respondents 16 are satisfied and 4 are not. The respondents who are satisfied were customers of Apple and Samsung. This shows that APPLE is producing better handsets and technology than the other brands like Nokia and Samsung.

3. Which price range of mobile phone suites you the most?

Price Range	Number of respondents
High Range	7
Medium Range	10
Low Range	3

Interpretation:-

Out of 20 respondents, 10 prefer medium range phones, 7 prefer high range and 3 prefer low range phones. This shows that, maximum customers prefer medium range phones that start from Rs.10,000 to Rs. 20, 000. With the changing market of mobile phones most of the companies are launching medium range phones. APPLE still dominates the market being an expensive Brand.

4. According to you, which advertising media can be used by mobile companies to increase the awareness among the people?

Different medias	Number of respondents
Television	6
Radio	0
Internet	10
Hoardings	4

Interpretation:-

Out of 18 respondents, 6 selected television as an advertising media that can increase the awareness, while 4 selected hoardings, 10 selected internet and 0 selected radio. Television presents advertisement in much more effective manner but people find it more accessible on Internet as the knowledge of it is increasing.

ANALYSIS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

- Apple , Samsung and Micromax are the favorite as brands among the customers in Delhi Market, closely followed by others.
- Apple ranks at the top when it comes to brand preference ahead of other brands.
- The brand awareness of APPLE mobile phones is 90%. This shows that people are aware of APPLE mobile phones. But, there are people who are unaware because they are not interested in generally expensive mobile phones.
- About 50% of the people who were surveyed prefer to purchase a mobile phone of a medium range price. This shows that customers are ready to pay for the mobile phones that have new features and are value for money. However, Apple is still on the wish list of many people who strive for status symbol.
- The general opinion about APPLE mobile phones is that it is either good or satisfactory.

CONCLUSION OF THE STUDY: The study concluded that SAMSUNG has the maximum brand preference as compared to other brands. APPLE is well trusted and appreciated brand. Its market share is relatively less but it can increase with promotions and advertisings.

Most of the dealers are selling more than one brand. They sell different brands to gain more volume & more availability to the customers. So dealer's preference to push a particular brand to the customer plays a major role in the mobile market.

According to the dealers advertising & promotional schemes along with other schemes also affect the consumer's willingness. Aggressive advertising put into effect for a long time in the customers mind, which influence the people, are T.V, Newspapers & magazines.

Consumers prefer a MNC brand due to the quality & technological superior features. Consumers also judge the after sale service availability of the company before purchasing a mobile.

However, Samsung edges off the Apple by almost doubling its shares to 22.4% in the market whereas Apple stands at 11.8% for the first quarter.

REFERENCES AND BIBLIOGRAPHY:

- Apple Supply-Chain secret, Hoard Laser; 4th November 2011. <http://www.webcitation.org/62xFMUc3>
- Deutschman, Alan. "The once and future Steve Jobs". Salon.com. Archived from the original on December 2, 2010. Retrieved November 22, 2010.
- "Ruthlessness and lasers: Apple's supply chain revealed | Smart Shift | Executive | Financial Post". Business.financialpost.com. Retrieved December 24, 2011. <http://business.financialpost.com/2011/11/09/ruthlessness-and-lasers-apples-supplychain-revealed/>